

Faster and more Energy-Efficient Equation Solvers over GF(2)

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Abstract. In a recent paper by Banik et al. at IACR TCHES 2024, the authors have constructed hardware circuits to compute the Möbius Transform of a Boolean function using polynomial space. This core circuit is then used to solve equations over $GF(2)$ of degree d (where d is typically a small integer). In this paper we outline two improvements to the above circuit that make it faster and consume even lower energy. The first comes from an observation of the purely combinatorial part of the circuit which extracts input indices of a truth table where the entry is zero. We show that the process can be extracted using a new circuit element that has much lower critical path. We also identify that the principal circuit component that contributed to the overall latency of the solver is the **Expmob1** circuit that converts the algebraic form of a Boolean function to its truth table using a single cycle. We show that if suitably spaced pipeline stages are inserted in it, both the energy consumption and total circuit latency can be reduced. We end the paper by implementing our circuit on the **SAKURA-X** fpga device for solving quadratic equations of moderately sizes.

1 Introduction

Solving low degree equations over a finite field is an important problem in many cryptanalytic contexts. It is known that cryptanalysis of the block cipher LowMC [ARS⁺15] using single plaintext-ciphertext pair from an r -round instance of LowMC gives rise to a system of equations in the secret key-bits of algebraic degree $2^{r/2}$ [Din21]. The public key in the signature scheme PICNIC v3.0, consists of a single plaintext/ciphertext pair generated by $r = 4$ round instance of LowMC block cipher using the secret key as the block cipher key. In this case, finding the secret key requires solving a system of n Boolean equations of degree 4 in the n unknown bits of the key. Other than this, it is also known that forging a signature in public key signature schemes like UOV can be done by solving a set of quadratic equations over $GF(2)$ [KPG99].

The problem we target can be stated thus: given n variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , and m polynomials $f_i \in \mathbb{F}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ (for $i \in [1, m]$), where \mathbb{F} is any finite field, we want to find common solutions $x^* \in \{0, 1\}^n$, such that $f_i(x^*) = 0$ for all i . Over any finite field \mathbb{F} , the problem is NP-complete already when the polynomials are quadratic. For a complete analysis of the significance of equation

solvers in cryptography please see the discussion in [Bou22]. Hereafter, we will focus on the case of the Boolean field $\mathbb{F} = GF(2)$.

1.1 Previous Work

The hardware/software architectures for fast exhaustive search over $GF(2)$ were explored in [BCC⁺10, BCC⁺13]. The secret x^* is a point which all the f_i 's evaluate to zero. Thus at the point x^* , the truth tables of all the Boolean functions f_i will have the constant 0. Hence, we want indices x^* at which the logical **OR** of all the truth tables of all the f_i 's evaluates to 0. In [BCC⁺10], the Gray code technique is used to evaluate the truth table of each polynomial f_i . The space of points in the domain of the polynomials f_i is traversed in the order specified by the Gray code. Since successive codewords of the Gray code are known to differ in only one bit, it is more efficient to evaluate $f_i(g_{j+1})$ from the knowledge of $f_i(g_j)$, where g_j is the j -th codeword. Note that $f_i(g_0) = f_i(\mathbf{0})$ is just the constant term of f_i , thereafter if t is the only bit-position where the successive codewords g_j and g_{j+1} differ in, then we can use a Taylor-like expansion formula for Boolean functions to compute $f_i(g_{j+1})$:

$$f_i(g_{j+1}) = f_i(g_j) \oplus \frac{\delta f_i}{\delta x_t}(g_j). \quad (1)$$

Here $\frac{\delta f_i}{\delta x_t}$ is the 1st order derivative of the function f_i at the point x_t . It is common knowledge that the derivative has algebraic degree at least one less than the original function, and so if the derivative is not a constant or a degree one function we recursively evaluate the derivative term in Equation (1) with another round of Taylor expansion. The method obviously works best if the function f_i is quadratic, but can also be applied to evaluate moderately higher degree functions if some of the derivatives are precomputed. In a follow up work [BCC⁺13], the same authors proposed a hardware circuit for the problem, however, for only quadratic functions (that needed negligible amount of pre-computations).

In [BR24], the authors used Möbius Transform algorithm to evaluate the truth table of the Boolean functions f_i directly from their algebraic expressions. Although a straightforward algorithm to circuit conversion of the transform takes exponential amount of circuit resources³, the authors followed a recursive description of the algorithm used in [Din21] to construct a polynomial sized circuit for it. The authors then use this core circuit to sequentially evaluate truth tables of multiple Boolean polynomials and do the logical **OR** operation over them to extract the correct solution. The authors present many such architectures for the solver, the final of which is the most energy-efficient.

Limitations: One of the limitations of this work is that the analysis is limited to the finite field $GF(2)$, and analogous observations can not be made for higher order fields. For solving equations over higher order fields, the method using computation of Gröbner bases is still the most effective.

³Exponential in the number of variables n of the Boolean function.

1.2 Contribution and Organization

In this paper we first briefly revisit the architectures described in [BR24] to bring the reader up to speed with some mathematical preliminaries, the basic solver circuit and the related engineering issues. We then look at two improvements in the circuit elements used in design. The first is replacing the “encoder followed by decoder” circuit with an encoder and “ r OR $r+1$ ” circuit. While functionally these two circuits evaluate the same operation, the latter can be constructed to have a shorted critical path in hardware. Secondly, we observe that the longest combinatorial path in the solver circuit is an exponential sized Möbius Transform circuit (exponential in the degree of the Boolean function). We observe that by placing multiple pipeline stages in this circuit we can reduce both the energy consumption and latency of the circuit.

The rest of the paper is organized in the following manner. Section 2 presents the necessary background about the circuit architectures required to read the paper. Section 3 describes the “ r OR $r+1$ ” circuit. Section 4 discusses the introduction of pipeline stages in the circuit to reduce latency and energy. Section 5 present simulation results and a comparison of our architecture with [BR24]. In Section 6 we present an FPGA implementation of our circuit on the **SAKURA-X** device. Section 7 concludes the paper.

2 Background

Boolean function: An n -variable Boolean function is a map from $\{0,1\}^n \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ and it can be uniquely represented by its algebraic expression, called algebraic normal form or ANF. We can write the algebraic expression of such a function using the (\oplus, \cdot) basis:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = f(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}) = \bigoplus_{i \in \{0,1\}^n} a_i x^i$$

Here $i := i_0 i_1 \dots i_{n-1}$ is the binary string of length n , where i_j are the individual bits and x^i is defined as $\prod x_j^{i_j}$. The ANF vector $\mathbf{u} = [a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{2^n-1}]$ is defined as the 2^n -length binary string of all the a_i 's.

Example 1. For example, consider the 3-variable function $f = 1 \oplus x_0 x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_0 x_2$. We can write this as $x_0^0 x_1^0 x_2^0 \oplus x_0^1 x_1^1 x_2^0 \oplus x_0^0 x_1^0 x_2^1 \oplus x_0^1 x_1^0 x_2^1$. The function can be written as a length 8 bit-vector \mathbf{u} with bits at locations given by the binary strings 000, 110, 001 and 101 i.e. 0, 6, 1 and 5 set to 1 and the rest of the bits 0, which is to say that $a_0 = a_1 = a_5 = a_6 = 1$ and the rest of the $a_i = 0$.

The **algebraic degree** of the function (provided it is not identically zero) is defined as the maximum hamming weight of the string i such that $a_i = 1$. Thus in the previous example, the algebraic degree is 2. For functions having algebraic degree d , all the coefficients a_i such that $hw(i) > d$ are naturally 0. Since there exist exactly $\binom{n}{i}$ length n strings of hamming weight i , we can see

that the ANF of degree d function can be expressed using $\binom{n}{\downarrow d} := \sum_{i=0}^d \binom{n}{i} < n^d$ binary coefficients.

Truth Table: The vector of evaluations of a Boolean function at all its input points is called its **Truth Table** (therefore this is a binary vector of length 2^n). The truth table is another way in which a Boolean function can be uniquely represented. The ANF and the Truth table vectors of any Boolean function are related by the Möbius transform. Let $\mathbf{v} = [v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{2^n-1}]$ be the truth-table of the function f , with its i -th element being the function evaluation at the binary string representation of i , i.e. $v_i = f(i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{n-1})$. Then it is well known that \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u} are related as $\mathbf{v} = M_n \cdot \mathbf{u}$, where M_n is the Möbius matrix of size $2^n \times 2^n$. The i, j -th element of this matrix m_{ij} is given as

$$m_{ij} = i^j \text{ where the power operation is as defined earlier.}$$

The Möbius matrix M_n has been well studied in the literature: it is well known that the matrix is lower-triangular and involutive i.e. $M_n^{-1} = M_n$. Thus both $\mathbf{v} = M_n \cdot \mathbf{u}$ and $\mathbf{u} = M_n \cdot \mathbf{v}$ hold. We also have an alternative recursive definition of M_n in terms of tensor multiplication. If we define $M_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$, then for all $n > 1$, we have $M_n = M_1 \otimes M_{n-1}$, where \otimes is the matrix tensor product.

Multiplication of a vector by this matrix can be efficiently performed by the butterfly-like operations shown in Figure 1. The butterfly circuit shaded in blue is the multiplication of the input 2-bit vector by the matrix M_1 . The figure shows that for an n -variable function, the algorithm can be done in-place (without any additional memory) using $n \cdot 2^{n-1}$ xor operations and 2^n space.

Expmob1: The circuit obtained by arranging the butterfly layers as shown in Figure 1 was named **Expmob1** in [BR24]. It computes the Möbius Transform in a single cycle, but it requires $n \cdot 2^{n-1}$ two-input **xor** gates and so has size exponential in n . Notice that in the first butterfly stage, the top half of the input array (call it A_{top}) undergoes no transformation at all, whereas the bottom half (call in A_{bottom}) requires one layer of xor gates. Subsequent stages can be seen

Fig. 1: Möbius transform on $f = 1 \oplus x_0x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus x_0x_2$. The blue shaded component represents one butterfly unit. Note that the diagram is taken from [BR24]

as this basic operation executed on upper and lower halves of the output of the previous stage. In fact it was shown in [BR24], that the top and bottom halves of the first stage output were ANFs of the $n - 1$ variable Boolean functions $f(0, x_1, \dots)$ and $f(1, x_1, \dots)$ respectively.

Polymob1: The recursive nature inherent in the algorithm is clear from the previous description and was formally proposed in [Din21]. The polynomial size Möbius Transform circuit was constructed according to this description which is given in Algorithm 1. In the algorithm A_0 is the input algebraic normal form of a Boolean function f of n variables and degree d having only $\binom{n}{\downarrow d}$ coefficients. To compute the transform, first an additional space of size $\binom{n-1}{\downarrow d}$ is created (for storing the ANF of an $n - 1$ variable function) for the top and bottom halves of the input array, and the algorithm is called recursively on both halves. If the number of variables at the leaf stages of the recursion become equal to d then a circuit like **Expmob1** can be used to find the truth table of this smaller function in one cycle.

Algorithm 1: Recursive Möbius Transform [BR24]

```

1 Möbius ( $A_0, n, d$ )
  Input:  $A_0$ : The compressed ANF vector of a Boolean function  $f$ 
  Input:  $n$ : Number of variables,  $d$ : Algebraic degree
  Output: The Truth table of  $f$ 


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2 /* Final recursion step, i.e. leaf nodes of recursion tree */
3 if  $n=d$  then
4   | Use the formula  $B = M_n \cdot A_0$  to output partial truth table  $B$ .
5   | /* Use Expmob1 to do this */
6 end
7 else
8   | Declare an array  $T$  of size  $\binom{n-1}{\downarrow d}$  bits.
9   | /* Compute the 2 operations of the butterfly layer */
11  | Store 1st butterfly output i.e.  $A_{\text{top}}$  in  $T$  (requires no xors).
12  | Call Möbius ( $T, n - 1, d$ )
14  | Store 2nd butterfly output i.e.  $A_{\text{bottom}}$  in  $T$  (requires some xors).
15  | Call Möbius ( $T, n - 1, d$ )
16 end

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It is not difficult to see that notionally executing Algorithm 1, is equivalent to traversing the tree shown in Figure 2a in a depth-first manner, i.e. along the orange line. In [BR24], it was shown that this could be done using the circuit shown in Figure 2b. The total space required is given as $\sum_{i=0}^{n-d} \binom{n-i}{\downarrow d} \in O(n^{d+1})$, and it was shown that the total number of clock cycles required to execute the algorithm on the circuit was 2^{n-d} , i.e. one for each of the leaf nodes in Figure 2a. In each of these cycles the circuit outputs a partial truth table, i.e. that of the function f in which the first $n - d$ variables have been set to one of the 2^{n-d} binary strings.

There is one top-level register of size $\binom{n}{\downarrow d}$ storing the initial ANF vector A_0 . There is only one $\binom{n-1}{\downarrow d}$ size register to store the second level coefficients A_{top} and A_{bottom} . This means that if in the first clock cycle the 2nd register stores A_{top} , it must preserve this state till the entire left sub-tree rooted at this node is executed before it overwrites its state to A_{bottom} . Similarly there is only one $\binom{n-2}{\downarrow d}$ register to store potentially four ANF vectors (two each from the butterfly operation on A_{top} and A_{bottom}). Thus the engineering challenge was to ensure that each register at the successive levels store and preserve appropriate state vectors till it is time to overwrite them, and do this in a manner that minimizes the total number of clock cycles required to execute the algorithm. It was shown in [BR24] that this could be done by engineering the multiplexer signals $S[i]$ by using circuits of logarithmic depth.

The map $\chi_{n,d}$: The uncompressed ANF vector of an n -variable Boolean function has 2^n entries and mapping each coefficient into an array can be done canonically, i.e. for example the x_0x_2 term has coefficient 1 in Example 1: since the term can be written as $x^{101} := x_0^1 \cdot x_1^0 \cdot x_2^1$, the exponent vector 101 (5 in decimal) denotes the position where a one is inserted in the array. However for functions of a small degree d , coefficients of all terms of degree larger than d are zero and so in order to accommodate the potentially $\binom{n}{\downarrow d}$ non-zero coefficients in an equal length array there has to be a map $\chi_{n,d}$ from the set of monomials (or equivalently the set of n -bit strings of hamming weight at most d) to an integer in $\left[0, \binom{n}{\downarrow d} - 1\right]$. In [BR24], the authors define $\chi_{n,d}(D) = y$ if D is the y -th largest integer whose n -bit binary representation has hamming weight less than or equal to d . It was shown that the map was easy to compute, and had the additional property that for all $n-i$ bit integers $\chi_{n-i,d} = \chi_{n,d}$ and so while traversing down the recursion tree where one needs to work with functions of lower degree becomes seamless.

Fig. 2: The blue shaded part roughly represents one arm of the butterfly unit. Note here $(x, \downarrow d) := \binom{x}{\downarrow d}$. Note that the diagram is taken from [BR24]

2.1 Solvers

The authors in [BR24] present different architectures when the Polymob1 circuit is used to construct hardware solvers. Here we shall describe three of them.

Polysolve1: This is the simplest possible solver architecture and also the most straightforward. Given m polynomials $f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_m$ of degree d or smaller, we want to find the root $r \in \{0, 1\}^n$ which simultaneously evaluates to $f_1(r) = f_2(r) = \dots = f_m(r) = 0$. Combining the above in a single equation we get: $\bigvee_{i=1}^m f_i(r) = 0$. Figure 3a shows us the circuit architecture: there are m copies of **Polymob1** that outputs partial truth tables of the functions f_i of 2^d bits at a time. The **OR** of all the truth tables is computed to get the partial truth table of the Boolean function $\bigvee_{i=1}^m f_i$. Now the task is to find indices in the table for which the corresponding entry is 0. This is found by using a priority encoder that outputs the index of the first 0 of an input string. Thus this circuit although can not find all roots of a given equation system, it can certainly tell if the underlying system has a root or not, thus serving as a decisional oracle. Note that the figure shows a large critical path of the circuit which can be reduced by putting pipeline stages before and after the **OR** network.

Polysolve3: The architecture was then modified to output every root of any equation system. After one root is extracted by the priority encoder, the root is input to a decoder circuit which is functionally the opposite of an encoder. If we **OR** the decoder output and the original encoder input, the resulting string has one less 0, which is written back on to the register before the encoder. The process is continued over as many cycles it requires for the string to be all one. [BR24] contains an example of this process which we reproduce here for clarity.

Example 2. [BR24] Let $d = 4$, and let the **OR** of the truth tables be $T_0 = 1011\ 1111\ 1111\ 0111$. Then the priority encoder in the first cycle outputs 0001 which is the index of the first 0. The decoder outputs $D_0 = 0100\ 0000\ 0000\ 0000$, which after **OR** with T_0 becomes $T_1 = T_0 \vee D_0 = 1111\ 1111\ 1111\ 0111$, and has one less zero than T_0 , and is written back to **Reg2**. In the next cycle we get the next root 1100 from the priority encoder which decodes to $D_1 = 0000\ 0000\ 0000\ 1000$. Therefore we have $T_2 = T_1 \vee D_1 = 1111\ 1111\ 1111\ 1111$ which is now the all one string.

It was proven that if the underlying equation system had R roots, then the architecture takes $2^{n-d} + R$ clock cycles to execute.

Polysolve4: This architecture was introduced with a view to improve energy efficiency. First of all the authors observed that having m **Polymob1** circuits results in a lot of redundant computation. For example consider the case when $n = m = 50$, and the common solution-space of the first 10 equations is only around 90-100 vectors in $\{0, 1\}^{50}$. In that case it makes is easier to do the following: **a)** Take each root $r \in$ the common solution-space of the first 10 equations, and **b)** evaluate $f_i(r)$ for $11 \leq i \leq 50$: if all these $f_i(r)$'s evaluate to 0 then r is a root of the equation system. Note that this essentially amounts to evaluating

Fig. 3: Circuits for solving m equations. Note that the diagram is taken from [BR24]

around 40 Boolean functions over 90-100 points. So the idea is to have only 10 Möbius Transform circuits that extract the common roots of the first 10 equations then we can do the functional evaluations of the remaining 40 equations over this common solution-space using some other method. This is much better than using the Möbius Transform circuit 50 times, which is mathematically equivalent to evaluating the remaining 40 equations over all the 2^{50} points of its input space.

The architecture for **Polysolve4** is shown in Figure 4. As explained there are only $\mu < n$ **Polymob1** circuits, which produce the common roots of the first μ Boolean polynomials. To evaluate these roots over the remaining $m - \mu$ equations, there are two additional circuit elements introduced: (a) the Expander and (b) the Dot-product. The expander is a function from $\{0, 1\}^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^{\binom{n}{d}}$, that is takes an n -bit string r and produces a $\binom{n}{d}$ -bit vector \mathbf{r} that are the values of all the degree d monomials (arranged as per the map $\chi_{n,d}$) at the point r . If \mathbf{v}_i is the compressed ANF vector of the function f_i then the dot-product $\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{v}_i$ is actually the evaluation $f_i(r)$. It was shown in [BR24], that both circuits can be constructed in polynomial number of gates and depth. The evaluations are then forwarded to an **OR** and if all the values $f_i(r)$, for $i \in [\mu + 1, m]$ are zero then r is output as root.

Since a Boolean polynomial is on average “almost” balanced,⁴ assuming that the first μ equations are independently sampled, the common solution space of the first μ equations is expected to be around $\bar{R} = 2^{n-\mu}$ in cardinality. Since each root of this space is evaluated in the same clock cycle as it is produced, the total number of cycles the circuit takes is $\bar{R} + 2^{n-d} = 2^{n-\mu} + 2^{n-d}$. Since the

⁴It can be shown that $\Pr[|wt(f) - 2^{n-1}| \leq \sqrt{2^{n-1}}] > 0.8$ (for f sampled uniformly randomly from the set of n -variable Boolean functions), which means that Boolean functions are close to balanced with high probability.

Fig. 4: **Polysolve4** Architecture. Note that the diagram is modified from [BR24]. The components in the blue dashed boxes are the ones that have been modified in this work.

dot product circuits consume much less power than the **Polymob1** circuits, the setup is much more energy efficient than the **Polysolve3** solver.

Bounded-depth trees: The full-depth **Polymob1** tree has height $(n - d)$ and takes around 2^{n-d} clock cycles as seen in Figure 2a. If instead, we bound the height of the tree to $n - h$ (i.e. by limiting the number of vertically stacked registers in the circuit in Figure 2b to $n - h$), for some $h > d$, it follows that we obtain a new Möbius Transform circuit which completes in 2^{n-h} clock cycles, i.e. faster than the plain **Polymob1** circuit by a factor of 2^{h-d} . This would however require that the **Expmob1** circuit connected to the bottom-most register must be of h -variables instead of d -variables needed in **Polymob1**.

The total number of clock cycles is thus reduced from $2^{n-\mu} + 2^{n-d}$ to $2^{n-\mu} + 2^{n-h}$. However as explained in [BR24], increasing h arbitrarily does not result in energy/time of execution of the solver. This is because larger h ensures that the energy consumption and critical path of the **Expmob1** becomes dominant. Once this happens we can clock the circuit at lesser frequencies, which would increase the physical time of computation. Also many circuit components that follow the **Expmob1** unit, scale exponentially with h . This also ensures that scaling the value of h after a certain point is infeasible.

3 The circuit r OR $r + 1$

One of the sources of large critical path in the circuit is the “encoder-decoder-or” circuit that follows the **Expmob1** circuit. Since these circuits are connected sequentially one after the other, the total latency of this circuit element is the sum of the latencies of the encoder, decoder and the **OR** gate. From the discussion in Example 2, we see that the primary use of the “encoder-decoder-or” setup is to decrease the number of zeros in the input string one at a time. We show that this can also be achieved with a “ r OR $r + 1$ ” circuit. Which is to say the string r is first seen as an integer and incremented by 1, and the result is **OR**-ed with r . The following lemma is easy to prove.

Lemma 1. *Functionally the “ r OR $r + 1$ ” circuit produces the same output as the “encoder-decoder-or” combination.*

Proof. The behavior of the increment operation on a binary string is well known. If the string ends with 0 (i.e. the lsb of the string is 0) then it simply flips the lsb to 1 and keeps the remaining bits unchanged. Otherwise it replaces the least significant contiguous block of 1s in the string with a string of 0s of equal length. Then the 0 bit just preceding this block is flipped to 1, and the remaining bits are left unchanged.

Since $1 \vee 0 = 1$, when this result is **OR**-ed with the original string r , the least significant 0 of r is flipped to 1, and so the resultant string has one less 0 than the original string r . In the language of bit-strings this can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(case 1)} \quad *0 &\xrightarrow{\text{increment}} *1, \quad *1 \vee *0 \rightarrow *1 \\ \text{(case 2)} \quad *01^t &\xrightarrow{\text{increment}} *10^t, \quad *10^t \vee *01^t \rightarrow *11^t \end{aligned}$$

This is exactly what the “encoder-decoder-or” combination aims to do. \square

Furthermore the operation of the “ r **OR** $r + 1$ ” circuit is independent of the encoder operation, so these two circuits can be operated in parallel and not sequentially as was the case of the “encoder-decoder-or” combination. Thus the total latency of this circuit can be expressed as maximum of the two latencies, i.e. $\max[\text{encoder}, r \text{ **OR} r + 1]**$ which in theory should be much lower than the sum of the latencies of the encoder, decoder and **OR** gate. However there are some other factors to consider too. In the case of the parallel connection of the encoder and the “ r **OR** $r + 1$ ” gate, the circuit elements which drive this combination (which is typically a register) sees much higher load capacitance on its output ports (due to the 2 circuits both connected to it). This implies that the register needs much higher electrical charge and effort to drive this combination which in turn increases the signal delay across the output port a little. However in our simulations we found that the parallel combination still has lower latency.

3.1 Incrementer Architecture

If $r = r_{t-1}r_{t-2}\cdots r_0$ is the input string then each i -th output bit s_i of the incrementer can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} s_0 &= r_0 \oplus 1 \\ s_1 &= r_1 \oplus r_0 \\ s_2 &= r_2 \oplus r_0r_1 \\ &\vdots \\ s_i &= r_i \oplus r_0r_1r_2\cdots r_{i-1} \\ &\vdots \\ s_{t-1} &= r_{t-1} \oplus r_0r_1r_2\cdots r_{i-1}\cdots r_{t-2} \end{aligned}$$

The Boolean product sequence $r_0, r_0r_1, r_0r_1r_2, \dots$ is commonly known as a prefix sequence. Since the Boolean **and** operation is associative, the circuit implementing the prefix sequence can be generated using the so-called Parallel Prefix architectures that are known to compute these prefix sequences in logarithmic circuit depth asymptotically. For this work we experimented with three popular Parallel Prefix architectures, namely the ones due to (1) Brent-Kung [BK82], (2) Kogge-Stone [KS73] and (3) Ladner-Fischer [LF80]. The circuit diagram for the three architectures are shown in Fig 5. The three architectures have unique features as it applies to our case. For example, as can be seen in Figure 5, the Kogge-Stone architecture has minimum logic depth, with minimum fan-out, resulting in a fast circuit but with a large area. The Ladner-Fischer architecture also has minimum circuit depth but has a large fan-out requirement. The Brent-Kung topology has minimal area but slightly higher circuit depth.

Fig. 5: Parallel Prefix architectures over 8 bits. The sky-blue nodes represent AND operations between two wires.

3.2 Experimental verification

To gain a fair understanding of which circuit architecture would provide us with lower latency and circuit area, we decided to perform an experiment in which we asked the circuit compiler to synthesize a) the “encoder-decoder-or” circuit and b) “ $r \text{ OR } r + 1$ ” circuit on $t = 2^h$ input bits, for increasing values of h ($5 \leq h \leq 14$). The compiler used the Nangate 15nm standard cell library [MMR⁺15] for the synthesis and was instructed to minimize latency of the circuit. For (b), we used the three Parallel Prefix architectures to construct the incrementer circuit as outlined above. In addition we also synthesized the circuit where the synthesizer is allowed to optimize the “ $r \text{ OR } r + 1$ ” circuit as it sees fit, i.e. the source RTL code presented to the synthesizer only mentions the functionality of the circuit without mentioning any particular architecture to optimize it. Figure 6 shows us a comparison of the area and latencies of all the architectures. We can see that all the “ $r \text{ OR } r + 1$ ” circuits almost guarantee better latency than the “encoder-decoder-or” circuit. The Kogge-Stone architecture gives minimal latency but its circuit area is around double than that of the other parallel prefix and synthesizer optimized circuits. The other Parallel Prefix architectures have slightly higher circuit area as compared to the encoder-decoder circuit. So in the interest of latency minimization without imposing too high a penalty on circuit area one could use any one between the Brent-Kung, Ladner-Fischer or the Synthesizer optimized circuit to construct this functionality.

4 Pipelining of the butterfly stages in **Expmob1**

Once we use height bound trees for some $h > d$, the **Expmob1** circuit required in the architecture has to be from $2^h \rightarrow 2^h$ bits, which requires h levels of butterfly layers as shown in Figure 1. This combinatorial block becomes a source signal delay, which can be no longer ignored as h increases beyond a point. Since large

Fig. 6: Comparing Area/Latency of “encoder-decoder-or” circuit and “ r OR $r + 1$ ” circuits.

signal delay across combinatorial blocks increases transients and glitches across the circuit, it also leads to increased power and energy consumption [BBR15] (see also [BBI+15, Figure 2]).

4.1 Adding pipeline stages

One way to alleviate both these issues is by inserting pipelines inside the **Expmob1** block at regular intervals as shown in Figure 7. The pipeline not only cuts down on the latency across the block, it prevents the propagation of glitches from one register to the next. A complete **Expmob1** circuit with 2^h bit input would require h layers of butterfly circuits (see Figure 1). To break things up, we take shorter **Expmob1** circuits with w stages (for $w < h$) and place registers in between them. We would need $\lfloor h/w \rfloor$ such register insertions. The final stage (if h is not a multiple of w) needs $h \bmod w$ stages. Since the **Polymob1** circuit continuously produces output vectors these are then in effect pushed into the pipeline, thereby increasing the total operation time by only a constant value, i.e. the number of pipeline stages $\lfloor h/w \rfloor$ that we have chosen to insert. The trade-off over here is over the value of w . A smaller value of w ,

- ↑↑ ensures that the latency of the **Expmob1** pipeline remains bounded i.e. by w butterfly units,
- ↑↑ decreases the energy consumption in the combinatorial part of the circuit as we will show.

A larger value of w however

- ↓↓ increases the power/energy consumption in the sequential part, due to the larger number of register write operations that the circuit needs to perform inside the **Expmob1** pipeline,

Fig. 7: Converting the fully combinational **Expmob1** block to a pipelined circuit

⇓ increases the circuit area, since we have to place more (i.e. $\lfloor h/w \rfloor$) registers to construct the circuit.

Even though a large value of w reduces register writes, for example, a value close to or equal to h , it increases the signal latency and glitches in the **Expmob1** circuit itself. Thus it stands to reason that there ought to be a value of w at which the power/energy consumption and the critical path of the circuit is optimized.

4.2 Energy Analysis

In [BR24, Equation 5] the authors model the energy consumption of the **Poly-solve4** solver whose height is bound by the parameter h , which solves m equations in n variables (with μ **Polymob1** and $m - \mu$ Dot product circuits) as follows:

$$E(m, \mu) = (\mu \cdot P_{mob} + \mu P_{expmob} + (m - \mu) \cdot P_{dp} + C) \cdot (2^{n-\mu} + 2^{n-h}) \cdot T_{clk}, \quad (2)$$

where

- A:** P_{mob} is the power consumed by the **Polymob1** circuit. The authors show that this figure is proportional to the number of flip-flops in the circuit, i.e. $P_{mob} \propto \sum_{i=1}^{n-h} \binom{n-i-1}{\downarrow d} < C_1 \cdot n^{d+1}$.
- B:** P_{expmob} is the power consumed by the **Expmob1** circuit. It was shown that P_{expmob} varies as $h^2 \cdot 2^h$. The reasoning provided was similar to the one followed in [BBR15]. If we assume that each xor gate in the first layer of the butterfly consumes power proportional to 1 unit (see Figure 1), then due to the propagation of glitches from one layer to the other, each xor-gate in the second, third, fourth layers consume power proportional to $1 + \delta, 1 + 2\delta, 1 + 3\delta$

etc, where δ is some positive constant. The sum $\sum_{i=1}^h 1 + (i-1)\delta$ is a well known arithmetic series and is of the order $h^2\delta$. Since there are 2^{h-1} xor gates in each layer we can conclude that the power consumption of the **Expmob1** varies as $h^2 \cdot 2^h$.

- C:** P_{dp} is the power consumed by the Dot-product circuit. and C is the power consumed by the other circuit components. Both these components are significantly smaller when compared to P_{mob} , P_{expmob} .
- D:** T_{clk} is the clock period, and we have already shown that on average the circuit requires $(2^{n-\mu} + 2^{n-h})$ clock cycles to execute.

The authors chose to run the simulations at 1 GHz as at that frequency the contribution of the static power to the total energy consumption was negligible. For $m = n$, the best way to balance out the the two components of the clock cycle count is to have $h = \mu$, from where we obtain $E(n, h) \approx (h \cdot (P_{mob} + P_{expmob}) + (n-h) \cdot P_{dp}) \cdot 2^{n-h+1} \cdot T_{clk}$. Since both $P_{mob}, P_{expmob} \gg P_{dp}$, we have the asymptotical expression as follows: $E(n, h) \approx (h \cdot C_1 \cdot n^{d+1} + h^3 \cdot C_2 \cdot 2^h) \cdot 2^{n-h+1} \cdot T_{clk}$, where C_1, C_2 are constants of proportionality. The value of h at which a minimum is achieved depends on how much C_1 is larger than C_2 .

4.3 Due to Pipelined Expmob1 circuit

The changes introduced to the expression for $E(m, \mu)$ when the **Expmob1** circuit is pipelined will be primarily in the expression for P_{expmob} . Instead of being modeled as $C_2 h^2 \cdot 2^h$, we model this as the total power consumed in the w -stage **Expmob1** circuits (there are $\lfloor h/w \rfloor$ of them) and the $\lfloor h/w \rfloor$ registers of size 2^h bits each. In addition if $h \not\equiv \text{mod } w$, we need an additional $h \bmod w$ layers of butterfly.

Since there are only w slayers of butterfly the total power due to the glitches is proportional to $2^{h-1} \sum_1^w 1 + (i-1)\delta \propto w^2 \cdot 2^h$. Putting this together we can write (where C_3, C_4 are constants of proportionality)

$$P_{expmob,c} = C_3 \cdot \lfloor h/w \rfloor \cdot w^2 2^h + C_4 \cdot \lfloor h/w \rfloor \cdot 2^h = \lfloor h/w \rfloor \cdot 2^h \cdot [C_3 w^2 + C_4]$$

where $P_{expmob,c}$ is the power consumed in the combinatorial part of the circuit. However some power is also consumed in the register write operations. Each additional register is of size 2^h bits and there are a total of $\lfloor h/w \rfloor$ stages the additional power consumed due to these writes can be modeled as

$$P_{expmob,s} = C_5 \cdot \lfloor h/w \rfloor \cdot 2^h$$

Combining both the expressions, we have $P_{expmob} = P_{expmob,c} + P_{expmob,s} = \lfloor h/w \rfloor \cdot 2^h \cdot [C_3 w^2 + C_4 + C_5]$. For the energy consumed by the new circuit to be lower than that of the original **Polysolve4** circuit we need $C_2 h^2 > \lfloor h/w \rfloor \cdot [C_3 w^2 + C_4 + C_5]$. The exact values of the constants C_i obviously depend on the particular standard cell library used to construct the circuits. In the following section, we simulate the energy consumption for the Nangate 15nm standard cell library.

4.4 The solver **Polysolve5**

We now formally propose the solver family **Polysolve5**. The main changes over **Polysolve4** are the ones highlighted in yellow in blue dashed boxes in Figure 4. More formally, the changes are outlined as follows:

1. We replace the Encoder-decoder-or circuit with the “ r **OR** $r + 1$ ” circuit. We could use any Parallel Prefix architecture for the incrementer, and although we used the Brent-Kung architecture, this particular choice is left to the discretion of the implementer.
2. We replaced the **Expmob1** circuit with a pipeline, with w butterfly stages in each pipeline.

We varied the value of h and for each value of h , tried to find the value of w that results in the optimal energy consumption. We present formally the simulation results in the following section.

5 Simulation results

In this section we will describe the flow of simulation followed for each of the circuits reported in the paper. The design was described at the RTL level using a hardware description language and functional correctness was first verified. Thereafter the circuit was synthesized using the Nangate 15nm Open Cell Library [MMR⁺15] using *Synopsys Design Vision*, mainly to ensure that the results obtained can be reproduced readily. In order to ensure that equations are solved as quickly as possible, the circuit compiler was instructed to specifically optimize the total critical path of the circuit. A timing analysis is then performed on the synthesized netlist using sufficient number of randomly generated test vectors, which outputs the switching statistic of every node in the circuit. This information is used by a power compiler software to estimate the average power consumed by the circuit. Energy is computed as the product of the average power and the total physical time taken for the circuit to execute a given operation.

Figure 8 shows the comparative simulation results for the **Polysolve4** and the **Polysolve5** circuits for $n = 20$ and varying values of h . Note that we were unable to take measurements for larger values of n, h since each simulation takes close to 24 hours beyond this point. For these plots, we have only used the data-point corresponding to the value of w which yields the most optimum results in energy and critical path in the **Polysolve5** circuit. For complete tabulated simulation results, for all values of $w < h$, and $w \in [3, 6]$, please see the Tables 1,2,3 in the Appendix B. The plots show that we are able to achieve considerable reduction in critical path (of the order of 25-30%) for each value of h we have simulated. The reduction in energy consumption, is less pronounced, but is of the order of 10-15% over all the circuits.

6 Solving Fukoka-like challenges on FPGA devices

The Fukoka MQ challenge [fmq] is an online equation solving challenge. The Multivariate Quadratic polynomial (MQ) problem is the basis of security for

Fig. 8: Critical path and Energy results for **Polysolve4/Polysolve5** circuits

some proposed post-quantum cryptosystems [YDH⁺15]. The hardness of solving MQ problem depends on a number of parameters, most importantly the number of variables, as well as the number of equations, the size of the base field, etc. The challenge basically consists of m quadratic equations over n variables in some base field \mathbb{F} , whose roots one is asked to find, i.e.

$$f^{(k)}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{1 \leq i \leq j \leq n} a_{ij}^{(k)} x_i x_j + \sum_{1 \leq i \leq n} b_i^{(k)} x_i + c^{(k)} = 0, \quad \forall k \in [1, m]$$

The attacker is given all the coefficients $a_{ij}^{(k)}, b_i^{(k)}, c^{(k)}$. The goal is to find an answer $\mathbf{r} = [r_1, \dots, r_n]$ in \mathbb{F}^n of the above system. The website presents 6 different category of challenges: of which the most relevant to this work is **Type I**: where $m = 2n$ and $\mathbb{F} = \text{GF}(2)$ and **Type IV**: where $m = 1.5n$ and $\mathbb{F} = \text{GF}(2)$.

6.1 Type conversion

For each k , the coefficients $a_{ij}^{(k)}, b_i^{(k)}, c^{(k)}$ are presented in a graded reverse lex order. For example, let x_1, x_2, x_3 and x_4 be the four variables of the system with $x_1 > x_2 > x_3 > x_4$. Then for a quadratic system, the order of monomials should be $x_1^2 > x_1 x_2 > x_2^2 > x_1 x_3 > x_2 x_3 > x_3^2 > x_1 x_4 > x_2 x_4 > x_3 x_4 > x_4^2 > x_1 > x_2 > x_3 > x_4 > 1$. However we know that $y^2 = y$ for any $y \in \text{GF}(2)$, and so although the challenge includes coefficients for both x_i and x_i^2 these need to

be xored together before we convert it to the order given by the mapping $\chi_{n,2}$. We explain the algorithm to convert from the graded reverse lex order to our mapping in Algorithm 2 in the Appendix A.

6.2 Solving on the SAKURA-X

SAKURA-X is also named as **SAKURA-GIII**, was mainly designed for side-channel attack experimentation. The board has Xilinx 28-nm Kintex-7 FPGA device, which enables advanced measurement with on-the-edge technology. The board has Two Xilinx FPGAs:

- (a) Control FPGA: Spartan-6 XC6LX45-2FGG484C, that houses the FIFO and other control signals that feed into the cryptographic core of the second FPGA, and
- (b) Cryptographic FPGA: Kintex-7 XC7K160T-1FBGC that usually contains an implementation of the cryptographic algorithm targeted for side channel analysis.

As it has been alluded to, the board was designed for side channel experiments and not really intended for heavy calculations, and so the computational powers of the device are rather limited. For the purpose of our experiments, the control FPGA was clocked at 24 MHz and the equation solver was implemented on the cryptographic FPGA at 8 MHz.

The website [fmq] contains challenges starting at $n = 55$, however we could not solve them due to time and resource constraints given the size of the device. The largest solver circuit we could fit in the device was with $m = 83$, $n = 30$, $d = 2$ and $h = \mu = 12$. We randomly generated type **I,IV** instances of size $n = 45$. For type **I** we took the first 83 equations of the system and for type **IV** (which has around 67 equations), the remaining equations were taken as the all zero string (since any root satisfies the equation $0 = 0$).

Thereafter, we guessed the first 15 bits of the solution and converted the resultant bit string to a reduced equation system of 83 equations, in 30 variables as required. For each guess the reduced system of equations were fed to the circuit which in turn either returned no solution or one/multiple candidate solutions. Each run of 2^{15} guesses took around 4 hours to complete. Thereafter if the cardinality of the candidate system is 1, the candidate is output as the root. If not each Boolean function in the system was evaluated at the candidate points. Those which passed the system are output as roots.

7 Conclusion

In this paper we make two improvements to the **Polysolve4** circuit of [BR24] which reduced latency and energy consumption. We show that the process can be executed using a new circuit element that has much lower critical path. We also identify that the principal circuit component that contributed to the overall latency of the solver is the **Expmob1** circuit that converts the algebraic form of a

Boolean function to its truth table using a single cycle. We show that if suitably spaced pipeline stages are inserted in it, both the energy consumption and total circuit latency can be reduced. We end the paper by implementing our circuit on the **SAKURA-X** FPGA device for solving quadratic equations of moderate sizes.

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References

- ARS⁺15. Martin R. Albrecht, Christian Rechberger, Thomas Schneider, Tyge Tiessen, and Michael Zohner. Ciphers for MPC and FHE. In *Advances in Cryptology - EUROCRYPT 2015 - 34th Annual International Conference on the Theory and Applications of Cryptographic Techniques, Sofia, Bulgaria, April 26-30, 2015, Proceedings, Part I*, pages 430–454, 2015.
- BBI⁺15. Subhadeep Banik, Andrey Bogdanov, Takanori Isobe, Kyoji Shibutani, Harunaga Hiwatari, Toru Akishita, and Francesco Regazzoni. Midori: A block cipher for low energy. In Tetsu Iwata and Jung Hee Cheon, editors, *Advances in Cryptology - ASIACRYPT 2015 - 21st International Conference on the Theory and Application of Cryptology and Information Security, Auckland, New Zealand, November 29 - December 3, 2015, Proceedings, Part II*, volume 9453 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 411–436. Springer, 2015.
- BBR15. Subhadeep Banik, Andrey Bogdanov, and Francesco Regazzoni. Exploring energy efficiency of lightweight block ciphers. In Orr Dunkelman and Liam Keliher, editors, *Selected Areas in Cryptography - SAC 2015 - 22nd International Conference, Sackville, NB, Canada, August 12-14, 2015*, volume 9566 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 178–194. Springer, 2015.
- BCC⁺10. Charles Bouillaguet, Hsieh-Chung Chen, Chen-Mou Cheng, Tung Chou, Ruben Niederhagen, Adi Shamir, and Bo-Yin Yang. Fast exhaustive search for polynomial systems in F_2 . In Stefan Mangard and François-Xavier Standaert, editors, *Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems, CHES 2010, 12th International Workshop, Santa Barbara, CA, USA, August 17-20, 2010. Proceedings*, volume 6225 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 203–218. Springer, 2010.
- BCC⁺13. Charles Bouillaguet, Chen-Mou Cheng, Tung Chou, Ruben Niederhagen, and Bo-Yin Yang. Fast exhaustive search for quadratic systems in F_2 on FPGAs. In Tanja Lange, Kristin E. Lauter, and Petr Lisonek, editors, *Selected Areas in Cryptography - SAC 2013 - 20th International Conference, Burnaby, BC, Canada, August 14-16, 2013, Revised Selected Papers*, volume 8282 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 205–222. Springer, 2013.
- BK82. Richard P. Brent and H. T. Kung. A regular layout for parallel adders. *IEEE Trans. Computers*, (3):260–264, 1982.

- Bou22. Charles Bouillaguet. Boolean polynomial evaluation for the masses. *IACR Cryptol. ePrint Arch.*, page 1412, 2022.
- BR24. Subhadeep Banik and Francesco Regazzoni. Compact circuits for efficient möbius transform. *IACR Trans. Cryptogr. Hardw. Embed. Syst.*, 2024(2):481–521, 2024.
- Din21. Itai Dinur. Cryptanalytic applications of the polynomial method for solving multivariate equation systems over $\text{GF}(2)$. In Anne Canteaut and François-Xavier Standaert, editors, *Advances in Cryptology - EUROCRYPT 2021 - 40th Annual International Conference on the Theory and Applications of Cryptographic Techniques, Zagreb, Croatia, October 17-21, 2021, Proceedings, Part I*, volume 12696 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 374–403. Springer, 2021.
- fmq. Fukoka mq challenge. Available at <https://www.mqchallenge.org/>.
- KPG99. Aviad Kipnis, Jacques Patarin, and Louis Goubin. Unbalanced oil and vinegar signature schemes. In Jacques Stern, editor, *Advances in Cryptology - EUROCRYPT '99, International Conference on the Theory and Application of Cryptographic Techniques, Prague, Czech Republic, May 2-6, 1999, Proceeding*, volume 1592 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 206–222. Springer, 1999.
- KS73. Peter M. Kogge and Harold S. Stone. A parallel algorithm for the efficient solution of a general class of recurrence equations. *IEEE Trans. Computers*, 22(8):786–793, 1973.
- LF80. Richard E. Ladner and Michael J. Fischer. Parallel prefix computation. *J. ACM*, 27(4):831–838, oct 1980.
- MMR⁺15. Mayler Martins, Jody Maick Matos, Renato P. Ribas, André Reis, Guilherme Schlinker, Lucio Rech, and Jens Michelsen. Open cell library in 15nm freepdk technology. In *Proceedings of the 2015 Symposium on International Symposium on Physical Design, ISPD '15*, page 171–178, New York, NY, USA, 2015. Association for Computing Machinery.
- YDH⁺15. Takanori Yasuda, Xavier Dahan, Yun-Ju Huang, Tsuyoshi Takagi, and Kouichi Sakurai. MQ challenge: Hardness evaluation of solving multivariate quadratic problems. *IACR Cryptol. ePrint Arch.*, page 275, 2015.

Appendix A: Conversion from grlex ordering to $\chi_{n,2}$

The following algorithm converts from the graded reverse lex order to the coefficient mapping given by $\chi_{n,2}$. The initial array of coefficients of length $1+2n+\binom{n}{2}$ is X , i.e. if $n = 4$ by the ordering given in Section 6.1, X will be of length 15. For example, the polynomial $x_1^2 + x_1x_3 + x_4 + x_1 + 1$ is expressed as $X = [1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 1]$. Note due to $x^2 = x$ in $GF(2)$ the corresponding Boolean function for this polynomial is $x_1x_3 + x_4 + 1$.

Algorithm 2: Type Conversion

17 Conversion from *grlex* ordering to $\chi_{n,2}$

Input: n : Number of variables, X :Input Array of length $1 + 2n + \binom{n}{2}$

Output: Y :Output Array of length $\binom{n}{\downarrow 2}$ arranged as per $\chi_{n,2}$

```

18  $b \leftarrow 0, e \leftarrow 0, r \leftarrow 0, Y \leftarrow [0] * \binom{n}{\downarrow 2}$ ; /*Initialize Y to all 0s*/
19 for  $r \leftarrow 0$  to  $n + \binom{n}{2} - 1$  do
20   /*For the Quadratic terms*/
21    $\text{coff} \leftarrow X[r], \text{monomial} \leftarrow (1 \ll b)|(1 \ll e)$ ; /* "|" denotes
   bitwise-OR*/
22    $Y[\chi_{n,2}(\text{monomial})] \wedge = \text{coff}$ ;
23   if  $b == e$  then
24     |  $b \leftarrow 0, e \leftarrow e + 1$ ;
25   end
26   else
27     |  $b \leftarrow b + 1$ ;
28   end
29 end
30  $b \leftarrow 0$ ;
31 for  $r \leftarrow n + \binom{n}{2}$  to  $2n + \binom{n}{2} - 1$  do
32   /*For the Linear terms*/
33    $\text{coff} \leftarrow X[r], \text{monomial} \leftarrow (1 \ll b), Y[\chi_{n,2}(\text{monomial})] \wedge = \text{coff}$ ;
34    $b \leftarrow b + 1$ ;
35 end
36 /*For the Constant term*/
37  $r \leftarrow 2n + \binom{n}{2}, \text{coff} \leftarrow X[r], Y[0] \leftarrow \text{coff}$ ;

```

Appendix B: Post-synthesis simulation results for the Polysolve4 [BR24]/Polysolve5 circuits

We present tabulated results for the **Polysolve4/Polysolve5** circuits in the paper.

h	Polysolve4					w	Polysolve5				
	Area KGE	T_{cr} (ps)	T_{min} (ns)	Power (mW)	Energy (μ J)		Area KGE	T_{cr} (ps)	T_{min} (ns)	Power (mW)	Energy (μ J)
3	56.677	124.67	32681.49	20.177	5.2892						
4	70.332	119.63	15680.14	22.852	2.9953	3	71.848	87.16	11424.24	21.674	2.8409
5	85.475	122.94	8057.00	25.667	1.6821	3	93.917	92.11	6036.52	23.846	1.5628
						4	87.829	85.62	5611.19	25.437	1.6670
6	101.202	124.37	4075.36	28.102	0.9208	3	107.186	87.04	2852.13	28.357	0.9292
						4	105.434	86.04	2819.36	26.632	0.8727
						5	106.400	85.55	2803.30	27.078	0.8873
7	122.115	130.94	2145.32	33.520	0.5492	3	134.596	85.88	1407.06	36.923	0.6049
						4	126.904	84.82	1389.69	33.736	0.5527
						5	130.384	85.16	1395.26	34.571	0.5664
						6	132.471	86.13	1411.15	35.756	0.5858
8	153.022	141.29	1157.45	43.836	0.3591	3	172.130	85.99	704.43	48.014	0.3933
						4	179.482	87.94	720.40	51.883	0.4250
						5	163.209	85.52	700.58	44.647	0.3658
						6	168.176	85.25	698.37	46.599	0.3817
9	206.305	143.17	586.42	70.914	0.2905	3	280.905	96.83	396.62	91.668	0.3755
						4	259.777	91.37	374.25	81.078	0.3321
						5	220.002	88.91	364.18	65.446	0.2681
						6	229.775	88.82	363.81	68.853	0.2820
10	312.200	156.39	320.29	116.714	0.2390	3	447.557	96.72	198.08	152.315	0.3119
						4	395.395	98.16	201.03	129.845	0.2659
						5	429.240	97.88	200.46	147.796	0.3027
						6	342.199	94.02	192.55	108.305	0.2218
11	531.863	163.87	167.80	208.395	0.2134	3	774.851	113.87	116.60	268.379	0.2748
						4	646.017	100.80	103.22	215.541	0.2207
						5	769.716	101.21	103.64	268.503	0.2749
						6	567.352	100.38	102.79	188.983	0.1935
12	996.395	171.78	87.95	435.441	0.2229	3	1888.760	114.37	58.56	646.505	0.3310
						4	1613.352	119.56	61.21	560.009	0.2867
						5	1350.513	111.99	57.34	438.349	0.2244
						6	1515.018	116.04	59.41	530.501	0.2716

Table 1: Comparative results for the **Polysolve4 [BR24]/Polysolve5** circuits for $d = 2$. Power reported at 1 GHz.

h	Polysolve4					w	Polysolve5				
	Area KGE	T_{cr} (ps)	T_{min} (ns)	Power (mW)	Energy (μ J)		Area KGE	T_{cr} (ps)	T_{min} (ns)	Power (mW)	Energy (μ J)
4	348.237	152.21	19950.47	119.732	15.6935	3	370.207	124.94	16376.14	92.800	12.1634
5	413.541	153.15	10036.84	137.641	9.0204	3	438.083	123.50	8093.70	114.114	7.4786
						4	438.056	123.50	8093.70	114.136	7.4800
6	474.366	158.04	5178.65	178.054	5.8345	3	515.884	131.11	4296.21	90.369	2.9612
						4	511.413	127.62	4181.85	141.337	4.6313
						5	511.486	127.62	4181.85	141.604	4.6401
7	543.620	164.43	2694.02	207.352	3.3973	3	596.715	129.13	2115.67	107.855	1.7671
						4	592.670	131.21	2149.74	105.712	1.7320
						5	592.458	130.34	2135.49	105.712	1.7320
						6	592.149	129.83	2127.13	105.716	1.7320
8	622.745	174.61	1430.41	249.145	2.0410	3	707.752	124.14	1016.95	129.466	1.0606
						4	707.453	125.44	1027.60	129.464	1.0606
						5	680.006	124.52	1020.07	124.643	1.0211
						6	680.004	124.52	1020.07	124.643	1.0211
9	729.193	184.04	753.83	287.649	1.1782	3	912.111	124.76	511.02	171.456	0.7023
						4	870.505	123.05	504.01	160.586	0.6578
						5	829.050	123.46	505.69	149.740	0.6133
						6	828.755	123.46	505.69	149.738	0.6133
10	899.647	191.15	391.48	355.497	0.7281	3	1270.908	125.37	256.76	236.900	0.4852
						4	1161.546	127.37	260.85	212.755	0.4357
						5	1162.636	127.19	260.49	212.766	0.4357
						6	1066.555	129.67	265.56	188.682	0.3864
11	1209.696	195.50	200.19	560.684	0.5741	3	1989.728	132.68	135.86	364.723	0.3735
						4	1763.519	133.01	136.20	311.676	0.3192
						5	1760.819	134.40	137.63	311.674	0.3192
						6	1066.555	129.67	265.56	188.682	0.3864
12	1859.154	197.57	101.16	969.071	0.4962	3	4016.560	133.51	68.36	743.956	0.3809
						4	3530.580	133.82	68.52	628.289	0.3217
						5	3044.701	132.16	67.67	512.796	0.2626
						6	3044.183	133.14	68.17	512.807	0.2626

Table 2: Comparative results for the **Polysolve4** [BR24]/**Polysolve5** circuits for $d = 3$. Power reported at 1 GHz.

h	Polysolve4					w	Polysolve5				
	Area KGE	T_{cr} (ps)	T_{min} (ns)	Power (mW)	Energy (μ J)		Area KGE	T_{cr} (ps)	T_{min} (ns)	Power (mW)	Energy (μ J)
5	1621.265	208.87	13688.50	398.157	26.0936	3	1594.933	160.14	10494.94	258.322	16.9294
						4	1594.831	162.53	10651.57	258.653	16.9511
6	1866.587	213.82	7006.45	474.863	15.5603	3	1868.220	157.82	5171.45	495.868	16.2486
						4	1873.258	162.73	5332.34	493.577	16.1735
						5	1873.258	162.73	5332.34	493.717	16.1781
7	2084.936	225.81	3699.67	571.070	9.3564	3	2138.182	159.43	2612.10	585.247	9.5887
						4	2130.157	163.52	2679.11	362.901	5.9458
						5	2130.157	163.52	2679.11	362.901	5.9458
						6	2130.271	163.42	2677.47	362.896	5.9457
8	2372.227	238.72	1955.59	652.621	5.3463	3	2408.222	160.82	1317.44	422.525	3.4613
						4	2409.596	158.39	1297.53	422.535	3.4614
						5	2384.429	159.69	1308.18	417.688	3.4217
						6	2383.904	155.13	1270.82	417.668	3.4215
9	2659.779	247.40	1013.35	765.022	3.1335	3	2769.321	162.33	664.90	499.352	2.0453
						4	2733.671	156.22	639.88	488.443	2.0007
						5	2697.118	157.77	646.23	477.580	1.9562
						6	2697.119	157.77	646.23	477.580	1.9562
10	2996.840	262.67	537.95	933.736	1.9123	3	3254.323	159.34	326.33	597.959	1.2246
						4	3188.238	161.57	330.90	573.866	1.1753
						5	3188.602	158.40	324.40	573.867	1.1753
						6	3088.427	158.75	325.12	549.725	1.1258
11	3677.842	264.61	270.96	1192.6	1.2212	3	4146.645	167.55	171.57	756.142	0.7743
						4	3924.798	167.25	171.26	703.132	0.7200
						5	3924.758	164.30	168.24	703.138	0.7200
						6	3694.089	166.94	170.95	650.107	0.6657
12	4908.635	281.91	144.34	1831.8	0.9378	3	6292.108	159.35	81.59	1745.4	0.8900
						4	5804.803	153.69	78.69	1618.7	0.8300
						5	5317.195	154.70	79.21	930.600	0.4765
						6	5319.151	155.43	79.58	930.630	0.4765

Table 3: Comparative results for the **Polysolve4** [BR24]/**Polysolve5** circuits for $d = 4$. Power reported at 1 GHz.